

Fractality and chaos of primes like from Weierstrasse'a function

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Abstract: In this paper, we point out the fractal structure of the prime number distribution by a novel approach of dividing each prime number by its position in the prime number sequence. The sequence obtained in this way approximates the logarithmic curve, although the two distributions do not coincide perfectly. Analyzing the difference between the sequence based on prime numbers and the logarithmic function, we observe that their mutual deviation resembles the Weierstrass function and exhibits fractal features and also chaotic. Using the box method, we calculate the dimension $D=1,837$ and the Lyapunov exponent $\lambda = 0,415$ of the prime number series, which indicates its complex structure. These results contribute to the understanding of the nature of prime numbers and offer new insights into the potential fractal behavior and chaotic of their distribution.

Keywords:

prime numbers, fractals, Weierstrass function, fractal dimension, box method, chaos, Lyapunov exponent

Introduction.

Primes, as fundamental elements of number theory, have long fascinated mathematicians. Despite their irregular nature, many patterns and hypotheses have been proposed to better understand their distribution. The famous prime number theorem offers a logarithmic approximation to their distribution, showing that the density of primes decreases logarithmically as the numbers grow (Apostol, 1976). However, many questions remain

unanswered about the deeper structure of primes and whether they follow specific patterns beyond this logarithmic approximation. In this paper, we investigate the distribution of primes by a unique approach of dividing each prime by its position in the sequence, which produces a new sequence. This sequence shows similarities to a logarithmic function, suggesting a correlation between the distribution of primes and the logarithmic curve (Hardy & Wright, 2008). However, our analysis reveals that this connection is not exact. To qualify this difference, we examine the deviation between the prime-based sequence and the logarithmic function and then analyze the resulting difference sequence. Interestingly, this difference sequence exhibits fractal-like behavior, as can be seen when compared to the Weierstrass function, known for its non-differentiable and fractal features (Edgar, Gerald A., 1993). This sequence is also reminiscent of the chaotic changes on financial stock exchanges. To explore this issue, we use the box method, a standard approach in fractal analysis (Schroeder, 1991), and determine the fractal dimension and also the value of the Lyapunov exponent of this difference sequence. Our results suggest that the distribution of primes has a fractal and chaotic structure, an observation that may have important implications for prime number theory and related fields. Perhaps the prime numbers were generated by some recursive procedure that is hidden from us.

Analysis of prime number series.

Prime numbers, being among the most fundamental objects in mathematics, exhibit interesting properties in the context of decomposition. Let us analyze the behavior of successive primes by dividing them by their numbers. The resulting sequence can be written as:

$$x_i = \frac{p_i}{i} \quad (1)$$

where p_i is the i -th prime number and i denotes its number in the prime series.

Figure 1 shows a graph of x_i values that shows how the primes are distributed when divided by their numbers. To better understand this structure, we have plotted these results against the graph of the natural logarithm:

$$y_i = \ln(i) \quad (2).$$

Fig. 1. Common graph of calculations. x - dividing of a primes by its index (formula 1);

y - logarithm of the index; d - difference of x - y graphs.

The "x" and "d" graphs appear to be smooth lines, but they are not. They have fluctuations that are so small that they are not visible at this scale. The "y" line, on the other hand, is a smooth line.

We observe that both graphs – x_i and y_i – are shifted relative to each other, and the primes form a logarithmic curve. This comparison shows an interesting pattern that may suggest that the distribution of primes is somehow related to the logarithmic function. However, when we superimpose both graphs, we notice that they do not match perfectly. This difference indicates irregularities in the distribution of primes. To investigate this, we can calculate the difference between x_i and y_i , obtaining a new sequence:

$$d_i = x_i - y_i \quad (3).$$

The graph of this difference (also shown in Fig. 1) clearly shows a slight upward slope, which means that the prime numbers do not follow a logarithmic function exactly. We can conclude that the sequence of prime numbers obtained in this way is not perfectly logarithmic, although very close to it. This is a fascinating phenomenon in itself and raises questions about

the nature of the prime number distribution. To better understand the structure of the sequence d_i , let us look at its detailed course in Fig. 2, where a fragment of the graph of d is shown.

Fig. 2. Fragment of graph d from Fig. 1.

An interesting observation is that this graph resembles the Weierstrass function – a function of a fractal nature, known for not being differentiable at any point. The Weierstrass function is an example of a fractal function, which suggests the possibility of a fractal nature in the prime number distribution as well. To assess this possibility, the fractal dimension of the graph of d was analyzed over a wider range of i values, namely from $i=500000$ to $i=540000$ (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Extended fragment of graph d from Fig. 1.

The study used the box method, commonly used to determine the fractal dimension, which consists of covering the graph with boxes of decreasing size and examining the extent to which the graph fills the space. The result $D=1,837$ was obtained. To verify the correctness of the box method used, the fractal dimension of the Weierstrass function was also determined for different values of the parameters a and b , which shape this function. The obtained values were very close to the results obtained from the theoretical formula for the fractal dimension of the Weierstrass function graph:

$$D_W = 2 + \frac{\ln a}{\ln b} \quad (4).$$

The obtained value $D=1,837$ indicates that the distribution of prime numbers has a strongly fractal character. This means that prime numbers create a structure of high irregularity, which is consistent with the nature of fractal functions. Such a distribution is still a subject of research. The study of the fractal dimension of the distribution of prime numbers can have significant implications in number theory, which can be an inspiration for further research in this field. Nevertheless, in this work, the value of the Lyapunov exponent was also determined for the series of 100,000 d_i numbers under study. For this purpose, a method was used that analyzes sensitivity to initial conditions by tracking the intervals between the base value and its

disturbed copy (Kantz & Schreiber, 1997; Rosenstein, Collins & De Luca, 1993; Wolf, Swift, Swinney & Vastano, 1985; Eckmann & Ruelle, 1985; Sprott, 2003). The Lyapunov exponent determined in this way is positive and has the value $\lambda=0.415$, which means that the distribution of primes is also chaotic (Berezowski, 2020).

Summary.

In this paper, we have shown that the prime distribution shows a remarkable, although imperfect, resemblance to the logarithmic function when each prime is divided by its sequential index. Although the prime sequence and the logarithmic function appear to be closely related, they do not coincide perfectly. The differential sequence, representing the deviation between these functions, shows a subtle but clear increase, indicating that the prime distribution does not completely conform to the logarithmic model. Furthermore, our analysis of the differential sequence suggests a fractal structure, which is evidence of its similarity to the Weierstrass function, known to have a complex, self-similar nature (Weisstein, n.d.). Computing the dimension of the differential prime sequence using the box method yielded a value of $D = 1,837$, confirming the fractal nature of the distribution. These results provide new insights into the intrinsic complexity of primes, suggesting that their distribution may be governed by a fractal pattern. The implications of this fractal structure go beyond the theoretical investigations of this work and may affect fields that rely on the properties of prime numbers, such as cryptography and chaos theory. Further research is therefore needed. In this work, the value of the Lyapunov exponent from the d_i series closely related to prime numbers was also determined. A positive value of this exponent indicates that the distribution of prime numbers is chaotic. Both the fractal dimension and the positive Lyapunov exponent may suggest that prime numbers can be generated by an unknown recursive formula.

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